

Glenna2 Nordic Cloud

Aim 3 Target 4

D2: Install and optimize the AI/ML platform for enabling NGT AI/ML workflows

Document identifier:	NeIC-Glenna2-Aim3target_4_D2
Date:	26/03/2020
Activity:	Aim3 Target 4
Lead Partner:	SIGMA
Document Status:	APPROVED
Dissemination Level:	PUBLIC
Document Link:	https://wiki.neic.no/wiki/Glenna2 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3752622

Abstract

Description: This is a report about the work to enable an immunology-focused deep learning pipeline which was prototyped on the NIRD Service Platform as part of Glenna2 Aim3. It briefly introduces the pipeline and its software dependencies, describes the work being done, feedback from the users and lessons learnt.

Use case	2
Work being done	4
Feedback from the users	5
Lessons learnt	5
User interaction	5
Technical work/environment	6
Project environment	6

Glenna2 AI report on D2 “Install and optimize the AI/ML platform for enabling NGT AI/ML workflows”

Greiff-Lab/UiO (Victor Greiff, Rahmad Akbar, greifflab.org), USIT/UiO (Thierry Toutain, Thomas Röblitz)

This is a short report about the work to enable an immunology-focused deep learning pipeline which was prototyped on the NIRD Service Platform. It briefly introduces the pipeline and its software dependencies, describes the work being done, feedback from the users and lessons learnt.

Use case

Figure 1 shows the main building blocks of the deep learning workflow as it was implemented on Fram. This workflow has been implemented for the following publication: <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/759498v5>. The users wished to have this replicated onto the NIRD Service Platform as identical as possible. This required to build and run a container with the following capabilities:

- login for users of a specific NIRD project,
- being able to run commands from the command line,
- having standard deep learning software packages pre-installed,
- access to a GPU, *and*
- access to data stored under a NIRD storage project.

Below is a list of the main Python packages (with version if important) needed to run the workflow:

- TensorFlow >= 1.13.1
- Python 3.64
- matplotlib.pyplot
- sklearn.model_selection
- unicodedata
- re
- numpy
- pandas

Figure 1. Building blocks of the deep learning workflow. For further details, see Methods section of this publication: <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/759498v5>.

Work being done

Fortunately, we could reuse an existing container which lets a user login via ssh. Staff working on the NIRD Service Platform had set up a repository with default configuration, allocated sufficient hardware resources

(GPU, CPU and RAM) and linked the NIRD storage space to the container such that the initially running container had many requirements already satisfied.

After we introduced ourselves to how to use the CI/CD environment, we modified the Dockerfile of the existing container to add software packages. First, we added Miniconda3 as package manager. Second, we created a new environment named python3.6. Third, we added all the necessary software packages. Below are the two directives we have used to implement these steps:

```
# miniconda3, python3.6 environment with user's application stack
COPY Miniconda3-latest-Linux-x86_64.sh /root
RUN bash /root/Miniconda3-latest-Linux-x86_64.sh -b -p /opt/miniconda3 \
  && export PATH=/opt/miniconda3/bin:$PATH \
  && echo 'export PATH=/opt/miniconda3/bin:$PATH' >> /etc/profile.d/miniconda3.sh \
  && echo 'source /opt/miniconda3/bin/activate' >> /etc/profile.d/miniconda3.sh \
  && source /opt/miniconda3/bin/activate \
  && conda update -y conda \
  && conda create -y --name python3.6 \
  && conda activate python3.6 \
  && echo 'python 3.6.*' >> /opt/miniconda3/envs/python3.6/conda-meta/pinned \
  && echo 'cudatoolkit 10.0.*' >> /opt/miniconda3/envs/python3.6/conda-meta/pinned \
  && conda install -y matplotlib \
  && conda install -y numpy \
  && conda install -y pandas \
  && conda install -y python \
  && conda install -y scikit-learn \
  && conda install -y tensorflow-gpu
```

For compatibility reasons, we pinned the versions of Python to 3.6.* and CUDA toolkit to 10.0.*. Also, some packages (unicodedata and re) were left out as they were not possible to install.

While the container image was built successfully, it could not be uploaded to the repository used for the NIRD Service Platform. After several rounds of trial-and-error it seemed we had to skip at least the tensorflow-gpu package installation into the container image. We opted to install no software packages within the container and did install all necessary packages from within a running container into the project's storage space. We suspect that this problem is related to the size of the container image (a few gigabytes) or a timeout for uploading images to the repository.

Feedback from the users

The users have been using the instance productively and their overall experiences have been highly satisfactory. They would be very much interested in continuing to use the server.

Question: Did you notice any difference because the “server” runs as a container?

Answer: We did not notice any difference from a “natively running server”, apart from large memory usage: the server uses about 60GB of memory in its idle state/without any computation running.

Question: Overall experience getting your application to run? (difficult/easy, fast/slow, ...)

Answer: Easy and fast.

Question: Overall experience using the NIRD service platform? (no difference to normal server/different to Fram/...)

Answer: Very good, similar to normal server, no queue.

Question: Future plans/interest in using the NIRD service platform? ((very) interested, (very) interested if time, (very) interested if more GPU resources available, (very) interested if environment/own container more stable, (very) interested if interface exactly the same as on Fram (batch jobs))

Answer: Very interested in more GPUs, not interested in the same interface as on Fram, have not used containers.

Question: Do you have any estimate on how much faster your pipeline runs on the server (compared to Fram)?

Answer: The pipeline runs about 20 times faster than on Fram. The main reason for this speed-up is the use of a very performant GPU (NVIDIA V100).

Lessons learnt

User interaction

After an initial meeting in June 2019 where the users explained the deep learning pipeline and milestones for work have been agreed on, the partners met regularly (weekly/bi-weekly) to track progress. The meetings were temporarily suspended for about 4 weeks during vacation period (July & August 2019), and no meetings were conducted after the technical staff went into parental leave in mid-October 2019 (by then all technical work was finished). In between meetings and after mid-October 2019, we synchronized each other via emails. Overall the interaction between the users and the project staff was conducted professionally and very effectively.

Technical work/environment

System administrators of the NIRD Service Platform provided excellent support to the project. Some tutorial or document on standard deployments and important features of the NIRD Service Platform might have helped to perform the technical work even more quickly. To date the biggest issue deploying similar containers to a more widespread user base seems that there is some limit on the size of the container. It is assumed that it is not the size of the container image itself but rather some timeout to get the image uploaded to the repository (this is part of the build pipeline in the GitLab CI/CD setup). A workaround might be to let one use containers from external repositories as is the case for the NIRD toolkit. Nevertheless, the GitLab CI/CD service was a welcome environment to use for this project.

Project environment

The project was first discussed in late 2018, however the project start was delayed to early June 2019 which severely limited the time available to achieve more than a simple setup. Particularly, for such tiny projects more agility at the project owner and project management could greatly increase the appeal to users. In such exploratory work it is important to try out many options which requires sufficient project duration. Often technical staff has many other duties which cannot always be rescheduled on short notice.